

Some Aspects of Uptake of Zinc by Calcium Hydroxylapatite and the Effect of such Incorporation in the Solubility of the Bone Mineral

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The uptake of zinc by the synthetic calcium hydroxylapatite is facilitated by increase in Zn^{2+} concentration, a decrease in pH of medium of exchange and in the particle size of calcium hydroxylapatite. Absorption of Zn^{2+} and its accompanying diffusion into the interior of the crystals explain the mechanism of exchange.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite which is also called bone mineral ($CaHA$), $Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$ is the major inorganic crystalline component of human skeletal system¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement of reactions². $Ca^{2+} \rightarrow Zn^{2+}$ replacement in $CaHA$ is of extreme biological significance as it explains the mechanism of incorporation of zinc into human skeletal system according to the following equation

The incorporation of zinc into viva due to environmental pollution has acquired importance currently and so the study of the uptake of zinc by $CaHA$ and the effect of such incorporation in the solubility of bone mineral has been thoroughly investigated with synthetic samples and reported in this paper.

Experimental

Pure and homogeneous sample of $CaHA$ ³ for the study of the dependence of uptake of zinc by $CaHA$ and the samples of $CaHA$ containing varying quantities of zinc in the form of solid solution⁴ for the study of the effect of incorporation of zinc in the solubility of bone mineral were prepared by co-precipitation—a method specially worked out for this purpose. The chemical composition of these samples were determined^{5,6}.

The dependence of uptake of zinc by $CaHA$ on factors like pH in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, concentration of Zn^{2+} ion in the range between 0.01M to 0.1M of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ and a particle size between 60 to 320 mesh (B.S.S.) and the kinetics of $Ca^{2+} \rightarrow Zn^{2+}$ exchange were investigated. 0.2 g of $CaHA$ was equilibrated with a solution of 100 ml of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ (AR) by shaking in air tight polythene containers mechanically changing the

factors effecting the uptake under investigation each time while other factors were kept constant. The experimental assembly was kept in a thermally insulated cabin maintained at $37^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ to stimulate biological conditions. At the end of the desired period of equilibration the contents were filtered through IG_4 crucible. The residue was washed with a doubly distilled water till it is free from the absorbed zinc and the calcium and the zinc content of the residue was determined⁵.

The effect of the incorporation of zinc in the solubility of bone mineral was carried out as follows. The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro analytical determination of phosphate⁶ in the samples after equilibration. Potassium acid phthalate—sodium hydroxide and veronal—HCl were used as buffer combinations. The pH was measured with a line operated Beckmann pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. 0.2 g of 200 mesh (B.S.S.) of each of the sample was added to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in carbon-dioxide free double distilled water taken in air tight polythene container and were shaken mechanically at regulated speed at $37^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. At the desired period of equilibration the samples were separately filtered through IG_4 crucible and the phosphate content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically⁶.

Results and Discussion

The results of uptake of zinc by $CaHA$ was represented diagrammatically in Fig. 1. The uptake of Zn^{2+} by $CaHA$ was found to (i) decrease with increase of pH of the medium of equilibration in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, (ii) increase with increase of concentration of Zn^{2+} and (iii) increase with decrease in particle size of $CaHA$. The uptake of Zn^{2+} is found to be very rapid

Fig. 1AB Uptake of Zinc by Calcium hydroxylapatites.

Fig. 1CD. Uptake of Zinc by Calcium hydroxylapatites.

initially within the first 60 min (22 wt%) and remains almost constant (Fig. 1D). The uptake varies linearly from 28 to 12 wt% as the pH decreases from 8.0 to 5.0 (Fig. 1A), it was also a linear function of increase from 12.5 to 30 wt% as the medium of Zn(NO₃)₂ sol. increases from 0.01 to 0.1M (Fig. 1B). Fig. 1C shows that the uptake under a given set of experimental conditions increases from 11.2 to 28.25 wt% as the mean radius of the particles decreases from 320 to 60μ.

The results of incorporation of Zn²⁺ in the solubility of bone mineral was represented diagrammatically in Fig. 2. The dependence of solubility on

(i) the pH of medium of equilibration over physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, (ii) the zinc content in the sample at a given pH was investigated. It was observed that (i) the solubility of a given sample decreases with increase of pH of the dissolving medium (Fig. 2B), which was due to the proton accepting tendency of (PO₄)³⁻ in the dissolving medium⁷ and (ii) at a given pH the solubility decreased initially and increased after 60% mole of zinc content in the solid solution (Fig. 2A). This observation can be explained on the basis of (i) the common ion effect applied to solubility products of the solid solutions according to Milhofer⁸ and (ii) due to the

Fig. 2A. Incorporation of Zinc in the solubility of the Bone Mineral.

● At pH 6.0
 ○ " " 7.0
 ○ " " 8.0

Fig. 2B. pH Dependence of the solubility of Calcium Zinc Hydroxylapatites.

● CaHA
 ○ --- ○ Ca₂Zn₂HA
 ○ ZnHA

formation of covalent bonds on the introduction of Zn²⁺ in CaHA⁹. This explains the role of incorporation of Zn²⁺ in the solubility of the bone mineral.

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